

Incidence of Abdominal Tuberculosis in Patients Presenting With Peritonitis.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to find the incidence of abdominal TB in patients presenting in emergency department with peritonitis or acute abdomen.

Study Design: Cross sectional

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in surgical departments of Mayo hospital Lahore in a duration of 10 months from March 2018 to December 2018.

Materials and Methods: Patients with age greater than 15 years were included in study. Both genders were included on random basis. Informed consent was taken from all the patients or their relatives. Ethical committee approval was taken. Acute abdomen was labelled in patients who had generalized abdominal pain of 5 or more according to visual analogue scale either without or with vomiting and history of absolute constipation on one days or greater time period. Exclusion criteria included patients with end stage kidney, liver or heart abnormalities or patients who had malignancy. Exploratory laparotomy was done and a biopsy sample was taken from every patient with infected gut or from omentum and sent to a reliable lab for reporting. The case was included only in study if the sample revealed tuberculosis.

Results: Our study included 100 patients who presented in emergency with peritonitis or acute abdomen. 39.56 was the mean age. 25% cases revealed abdominal TB. Gender difference was insignificant. In patients with age of 40 years or less, incidence was much higher as compared to other groups where it was found to be 22 (30.9%). In patients with coexisting pulmonary TB, it was more common where it was seen in 6 (35.29%) cases.

Conclusion: In every 4th case with peritonitis, abdominal TB was seen and it had higher incidence in patients with age of 40 years or less.

Keywords: Peritonitis, Tuberculosis, Extra pulmonary TB

Introduction: Tuberculosis is one of the oldest diseases known to mankind and a lot of research, recent advances in its treatment regimens and better diagnostic modalities reduced its number in developed countries to much extent but in under developed countries like Pakistan and India, incidence is much higher. But recently even in developed countries, incidence is increasing again due to HIV and other comorbid conditions that weakens the immune system. (1, 2)

Tuberculosis can involve any system of the body which is labelled as extra pulmonary TB. It can involve brain, kidneys, spine or gastrointestinal systems. In GI system it can lead to the formation of strictures in gut in long standing cases causing obstruction and can also cause lymph nodes enlargement. Intestinal obstruction presents as an emergency condition which needs to be operated in emergency setting. The initial signs and symptoms of TB are nonspecific and multisystem can be affected by this disease. Simple laboratory investigations are insufficient in making diagnosis and advance and expensive diagnostic modalities like tissue histopathology, immunological tests or blood culture are required for proper diagnosis but these tests are expensive and time consuming. (3, 4)

Moreover, peritonitis caused by abdominal Tb pose a serious challenge to the operating surgeon as little preparations are made in emergency settings and he has to rely on his skills and judgment to find the extent of disease and section of the gut he has to remove in unprepared and often moribund patient. (5, 6)

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Table 1. Abdominal TB and Gender

Gender	Abdominal TB		Total
	Yes	No	
Male	17(26.98%)	46 (73.02%)	63 (100%)
Female	08 (21.62%)	29 (78.38%)	37 (100%)
Total	25 (25%)	75 (75%)	100 (100%)

In patients with age of 40 years or less, incidence was much higher as compared to other groups where it was found to be 22 (30.9%).

Table 2. Abdominal TB and age groups

Age Groups	Abdominal TB		Total
	Yes	No	
40 or less	22 (30.98%)	49 (69.02%)	71 (100%)
>40	3 (10.34%)	26 (89.66%)	29 (100%)
Total	25 (25%)	75 (75%)	100 (100%)

In patients with coexisting pulmonary TB, it was more common where it was seen in 6 (35.29%) cases.

Table 3. Abdominal TB and pulmonary TB

Pulmonary TB	Abdominal TB		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	6 (35.29%)	11 (64.71%)	17 (100%)
No	19 (22.89%)	64 (77.11%)	83 (100%)
Total	25 (25%)	75 (75%)	100 (100%)

Discussion: Tuberculosis is one of the oldest diseases known to mankind since ancient times and is among one of the common causes responsible for chronic diseases. Patients can present with varying and non-specific signs and symptoms. This is especially common in cases of extra pulmonary TB where the symptoms can be extremely vague and unspecified. Patients can present in emergency with intestinal obstruction or peritonitis.

In our study, incidence of TB in patients with acute abdomen was 25% which is in correlation with the previous studies done with similar settings. Farooq T et al in his study found the incidence to be 29.03% in patients with acute abdomen. (7)

Incidence of 16% was seen in another study carried out by Shaikh MS et al (8). Much higher frequency was seen in another study carried out in Pakistan where it was seen in 51.4% cases with acute abdomen (6). This great difference can be explained on the basis of high incidence seen in underdeveloped countries like Pakistan and India.

In patients with age of 40 years or less, incidence was much higher as compared to other groups where it was found to be 22 (30.9%). Previous studies done in similar settings showed the same results in which frequency is much higher in patients who had age between 20 to 40 years. (9, 11)

In patients with coexisting pulmonary TB, it was more common where it was seen in 6 (35.29%) cases. Similar results were seen by Shaikh MS et al in his study in which he found that 37.5% cases had concomitant pulmonary tuberculosis. (8)

Conclusion: In every 4th case with peritonitis, abdominal TB was seen and it had higher incidence in patients with age of 40 years or less.

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